

New records and shifting ranges of marine molluscs from Galicia (NW Iberian Peninsula)

Nuevas citas y distribuciones cambiantes en moluscos marinos de Galicia (NW Península Ibérica)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18235245>

Recibido el 5-VI-2025. Aceptado el 5-XII-2025. Publicado en línea el 30-I-2026

ABSTRACT

In recent decades, ocean temperatures have been subtly increasing, allowing species of molluscs from areas relatively close to Galicia, with a predominantly Mediterranean distribution and even from the Atlantic, but from southerly latitudes, to reach the Galician coast. These species, that were previously unable to reach them, are now able to do so, and at the same time, native species have been able to extend their distribution area in Galicia further north, where natural conditions did not previously allow them to do so.

This study provides new data for 14 species, seven of which are new records for Galicia. Six of these represent the northernmost known limit within their natural range in European waters, while five have been found alive for the first time.

RESUMEN

En las últimas décadas, las temperaturas oceánicas han aumentado sutilmente, lo que ha permitido que especies de moluscos procedentes de zonas relativamente cercanas a Galicia, con una distribución predominantemente mediterránea e incluso del Atlántico, pero de latitudes más meridionales, lleguen a la costa gallega. Estas especies que antes no podían llegar, ahora pueden hacerlo y, al mismo tiempo, algunas especies autóctonas han podido ampliar su área de distribución dentro de Galicia más al norte, donde las condiciones naturales anteriores no les permitían hacerlo.

En este estudio se aportan nuevos datos sobre 14 especies, siete de las cuales son nuevas para Galicia. Seis de ellas representan el límite más septentrional conocido dentro de su área de distribución natural en aguas europeas, mientras que cinco se han encontrado vivas por primera vez.

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KEY WORDS: Marine molluscs, shifting ranges, native species, new records, Galicia.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Moluscos marinos, distribuciones cambiantes, especies autóctonas, nuevas citas, Galicia.

INTRODUCTION

Global warming, together with factors related to human activities, is causing drastic and worrying changes to marine fauna in general and molluscs in particular. These changes occur in a number of different ways. For example, they change their thermal comfort zones (CASTRO-OLIVARES, DES & DE CASTRO, 2021) or colonise new spaces with ease, whether naturally or not, without posing a serious problem for their subsistence. In the ecosystems in which they establish themselves, they undoubtedly cause very negative impacts (RUÍZ ET AL., 1997; BYERS, 2002; KATSANEVAKIS ET AL., 2014). The warming waters favour these exotic, immigrant and cryptogenic species (STACHOWICZ ET AL. 2002) while the native species are less favoured by that same warming and in certain areas begin to be displaced by the former ones.

Galicia, in recent decades, and also affected by that warming, has become a hot spot, where species of molluscs that were not previously found here, find optimal conditions to settle with very high probabilities of success, arriving from relatively close areas such as the Mediterranean or, more rarely, from northern Europe.

Many species of molluscs have arrived in Galicia to settle successfully since the 1980s. While many of them have done so through aquaculture-related activities (TRIGO ET AL., 2025) some others cannot be linked to such activities but to global warming. There are other species whose arrival in our waters is only conceivable due to maritime traffic in any of its facets and which come from places, sometimes far away, whose intermediate or final destination is a Galician port.

The timing of when all these species were first detected in our waters, regardless of their mode of arrival, is as follows:

The first specimens of *Bolinus brandaris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Hexaplex trunculus*

(Linnaeus, 1758), *Fusinus rostratus* (Olivi, 1792), *Steromphala albida* (Gmelin, 1791) and *Tritia corniculum* (Olivi, 1792), were all found alive among oyster seed from Italy (ROLÁN ET AL., 1985), appeared in Ría de Arousa. The next species reported were *Gibbula adriatica* (Philippi, 1844) (ROLÁN & GARCÍA, 2000), *Pecten jacobaeus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (TRIGO, PÉREZ & ROLÁN, 2010), *Pseudosimnia carnea* (Poiret, 1789), *Simnia aperta* (GB Sowerby II, 1849), *Simnia nicaeensis* Risso, 1826 (FEHSE ET AL., 2010), *Naticarius stercus-muscarum* (Gmelin, 1791) (HORRO & ROLÁN, 2011), *Trinchesia ocellata* Schmekel, 1966 (TRIGO & GARCÍA SANTIAGO, 2012), *Cumanotus beaumonti* (Eliot, 1906) and *Cumanotus cuenoti* Pruvot-Fol, 1948 (ALMÓN, PÉREZ DIESTE & TRIGO, 2013), all of them in the Ría de Arousa. Subsequently, in Costa da Morte and Arousa, again, *Jujubinus gravinae* (Dautzenberg, 1881), *Curveulima dautzenbergi*, (Pallary, 1900) and *Laona pruinosa* (Clark W., 1827) (TRIGO Y PÉREZ-DIESTE, 2016). Later, *Atagema gibba* Pruvot-Fol, 1951, *Onchidoris bilamellata* (Linnaeus, 1767) and *Armina neapolitana* (Delle Chiaje, 1824) (ALMÓN ET AL. 2019). Already in the 20's, *Dendrodoris limbata* (Cuvier, 1804), *Trinchesia albopunctata* Schmekel, 1968 and *Trinchesia cuanensis* Korshunova, Picton, Furfaro, Mariottini, Pontes, Prkić, Fletcher, Malmberg, Lundin & Martynov, 2019 are reported in the Ría de Arousa and *Nemesignis banyulensis* (Portmann & Sandmeier, 1960) in the Ría de Pontevedra (PÉREZ DIESTE, TRIGO & ALMÓN, 2021). Finally, *Raphitoma ephesina* Pusateri, Giannuzzi-Savelli & Stahlschmidt, 2017 a species thought to be endemic to the Mediterranean is found, once again, in the Ría de Arousa (ALMÓN ET AL., 2024).

Galicia is a region located in the northwest of the Iberian Peninsula. Its coast extends throughout 1,498 km, creating a unique stretch on the Spanish

Figure 1. Location of Galicia within Europe and Iberian Peninsula with sampled locations.
Figura 1. Situación de Galicia dentro de Europa y península ibérica con lugares muestreados.

coast holding numerous *rías*, amongst which stands out Rías Baixas, very wide, located in the Atlantic façade and further north, Rías Altas, much smaller and presenting higher cliffs than Rías Baixas.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens obtained have been collected, as mentioned above, in regular samplings along the coasts of Galicia (Fig. 1). This work is supported by the data provided by specimens found, fishermen and hobbyists who have freely collaborated (Citizen

Science). These samplings are normally carried out by walking along the intertidal zone of the Galician coast, also including inspection of local fishing gear from small fishing ports, and scuba dives down to 30 meters depth.

Views of the whole specimens were taken with a Canon EOS 550D digital camera for the largest specimens and for the smallest, an Olympus SZX 12 trinocular stereomicroscope and an Olympus SC 180 camera.

The main identification characteristics and ecological information such as habitat, distribution and origin are given and discussed.

SYSTEMATIC DESCRIPTIONS

Class GASTROPODA
Subclass HETEROBRANCHIA
Order CEPHALASPIDEA
Family PHILINIDAE

Philine angulata Jeffreys, 1867 (Fig. 2A-E)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Caldebarcos, Carnota Beach; 42°50'31.81"N, 9°06'29.89"W; 23 Aug. 2023; J. E. Trigo leg. • 4 specimens; Same data as for preceding; 18 Sep. 2024; J.E. Trigo leg. • 2 specimens; Pontevedra, Nigrán, América Beach; 42°06'47.98"N, 8°49'44.88"W; 23 May 2018; J. E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg.

Shell: internal, generally translucent whitish colour, oval in shape and with the upper outer lip ending in a pointed projection. Sculpture formed by tiny excavations of the shell arranged in lines.

Known distribution: Amphi-Atlantic species with a natural distribution range covering from Greenland to Brazil on the American coast and from northern Norway to Mauritania, including the Canary Islands on the eastern Atlantic coast, and the Mediterranean (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; RAVEN, 2023).

Remarks: The sampling, dredging and inspection of sediments were carried out before 2015 in different points of the Galician coast (CADÉE, 1968; URGORRI & BESTEIRO, 1983; ROLÁN, 1983; OTERO & TRIGO, 1986; TRIGO & OTERO, 1987; OTERO & TRIGO, 1989), which resulted in the finding of different species belonging to the genus *Philine*, but never *P. angulata*.

From being an unknown species, it has become relatively common. That it is a species, which has been gradually making its way among the native ones. The reasons for this behaviour are not clear, since it is not an exotic species advancing towards the north or, as in exceptional cases, towards the south, being Galicia located in the middle of its European distribution. The progressive warming of seawaters, in this case, is not a factor to take into consideration, since this is a highly widespread species, ranging from polar to subtropical waters. Other factors should be explored, such as climatic, food-related and/or ecological ones, with diverse thermodynamic variables or a set of two or more, which would allow drawing valid conclusions, which now, are out of our reach, but the species may just have been overlooked.

This is the first record for Galicia.

Figure 2. A, B: *Philine angulata*, shells found on América Beach, Nigrán, Pontevedra (height 3.4 and 2.7 mm); C, D: inner and outer side of a shell found in Caldebarcos, Carnota, A Coruña (height: 2.5 mm); E: detail of shell sculpture; F, G: *Philine intricata*. Inner and outer sides of a shell found in Caldebarcos, Carnota (height 2.7 mm); H: detail of shell sculpture.

Figura 2. A-B: Philine angulata, conchas balladas en Playa América, Nigrán, Pontevedra (altura: 3,4 y 2,7 mm); C, D: interior y exterior de una concha hallada en Caldebarcos, Carnota, A Coruña (altura: 2,5 mm); E: detalle de la escultura; F, G: Philine intricata. Interior y exterior de una concha hallada en Caldebarcos, Carnota (altura: 2,7 mm); H: detalle de la escultura de la concha.

Philine intricata Monterosato, 1884 (Fig. 2F-H)

Material examined: Galicia • 2 specimens; A Coruña, Caldebarcos, Carnota Beach; 42°50'31.81''N, 9°06'29.89''W; 23 Aug. 2023; J. E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Same data as for preceding; 18 Sep. 2024; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Nigrán, América Beach; 42°06'47.98''N, 8°49'44.88''W; 23 May 2018; J. E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg.

Shell: internal, translucent, cylindrical and oval. Shell sculpture formed by chains of tiny excavations arranged in a line. Top of crested opening.

Known distribution: From French Brittany to Morocco including the archipelagos of Azores, Canary Islands and Cape Verde. Also in the western Mediterranean (MUÑOZ ET AL, 2019; RAVEN, 2023).

Remarks: Like the previous species, it had not been found in Galicia in previous samplings. Being in an intermediate place within its natural distribution

area, it is surprising that it had not been mentioned previously. It is possible that the water conditions or others in Galicia are not entirely favourable for this and other related species, or that it just has been overlooked. At certain times, with the right conditions, larvae are able to survive and subsequently, it is possible to find empty shells on the beaches. It can be considered that the populations are fluctuating and subject to the physical-chemical and environmental conditions that allow them to develop or not.

This is the first record for Galicia.

Order NUDIBRANCHIA
Superfamily DORIDOIDEA
Family DISCODORIDIDAE

Jorunna cf. onubensis Cervera, García-Gómez & F.J. García, 1986 (Fig. 3)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ribeira, shoal "Fanequeira"; 42°32'81.60''N, 8°56'84.00''W; 26 Feb. 2011; J. Pérez leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ribeira, shoal "As Agullas"; 42°30'40.70''N, 8°56'44.90''W; 7 Mar. 2019; J. Pérez leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ribeira, shoal "Petóns de Fora"; 42°33'01.60''N, 8°57'98.90''W; 5 Sep. 2019; J. Pérez leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Arousa Island, Punta Quilma; 42°32'31.85''N, 8°52'43.45''W; 14 Aug. 2009; J.E. Trigo leg. • 2 specimens; A Coruña, O Grove, Umia-O Grove-A Lanzada intertidal complex, Punta Silva; 42°28'09.90''N, 8°51'25.70''W; 19 Apr. 2011; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; same data as for preceding; 16 May. 2011; J.E. Trigo leg.

Body: Oval-shaped body with a convex profile, usually between 15 and 55 mm in length. Light brown coat colour, sometimes with pinkish or greyish tints, with dark spots of variable size and darker colour distributed randomly across the coat. Rhinophores with 15 whitish lamellae and, in some specimens, with a dark brown band in the subapical area. Base of the rhinophores, below the transparent lamellae. Foot a tone lighter than the general colouring of the body.

Known distribution: Andalusia, Catalonia, Southern Portugal, Asturias, Canary Islands and Madeira (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011).

Remarks: Species described from some specimens found in Huelva and whose distribution is focused almost entirely on the Iberian Peninsula. There is a previous record in the towns of Oviñana and Castropol in Asturias (ORTEA & MORO, 2016), and the next one would be in the South of Portugal (MALAQUIAS & MORENITO, 2000) being Galicia within its natural distribution area, although it had not been previously recorded here.

The specimens found in Galicia, although not kept for later studies, fully match the original description of this species. This would be, therefore, the first record for Galicia.

Figure 3. *Jorunna* cf. *onubensis*. Specimens found at different places in Ría de Arousa. Approximate sizes, from top to bottom: 3.5, 5.7 and 4.5 cm.

Figure 3. *Jorunna* cf. *onubensis*. Ejemplares hallados en diferentes puntos de la ría de Arousa. Tamaños aproximados, de arriba abajo: 3,5, 5,7 y 4,5 cm.

Superfamily PHYLLIDIOIDEA
Family DENDRODORIDIDAE

Dendrodoris limbata (Cuvier, 1804) (Fig. 4)

Material examined: Galicia • 20 specimens; A Coruña, Ribeira, Ribeira marina; 42°33'45.96''N, 8°59'18.56''W; 12 Jan 2024; J. Pérez leg. • 2 specimens; A Coruña, Arousa Island, Xastelas Beach; 42°31'52.31''N, 8°52'07.76''W; 22 Jun. 2019; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg. • 1 specimen; same data as for preceding; 12 Feb. 2020; J.E. Trigo leg. • 16 specimens; A Coruña, O Grove, Umia-O Grove-A Lanzada intertidal complex, Punta Silva; 42°28'09.90''N, 8°51'25.70''W; 19 Mar. 2011; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg. • 4 specimens; same data as for preceding; 19 Apr. 2011; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg. • 2 specimens; same data as for preceding; 16 May 2011; J.E. Trigo and J. Fernández leg.

Body: Flattened, with the mantle edges clearly exceeding the foot. Extremely variable colouration, from yellowish, greenish to brown and even black, with different hues, often with darker spots randomly distributed throughout the mantle. The mantle edges are wavy and scalloped with a narrow yellow band.

Known distribution: Mediterranean, although it has also been cited on the southern coast of Portugal and the Strait of Gibraltar (CALADO ET AL., 2003; CERVERA ET AL., 2004; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011). There are observations of this species on the Atlantic coasts of French Brittany (SEASLUG FORUM, 2000; GALIÀ-CAMPS ET AL., 2025) and British Isles (MUÑOZ ET AL., 2019). It is also recorded in Galicia (PÉREZ DIESTE, TRIGO & ALMÓN, 2021; GALIÀ-CAMPS ET AL., 2025).

Remarks: The spreading of this species in Ría de Arousa, where it was first found in Galicia, is as follows: the first specimens were found in March 2019, in the intertidal natural space Umia-O Grove. In samplings carried out back in 2020, they were already present on Arousa Island. In 2023, they were found on the north coast, in the Ribeira marina.

The distribution area of this species is expanding very quickly. Although it does not seem to compete with other species of native heterobranchs for food and apparently coexists in perfect harmony with

them, its ability to colonize new spaces is worrying, which so far only *Crepidatella dilatata* has been able to surpass. Other exotic marine molluscs that have previously appeared in Arousa find their expansion limited by contributions of freshwater from the Ulla River at the bottom of the *ría* and colder waters towards its outer periphery, initially remaining on its southern coast, where milder temperatures and more suitable geographical conditions facilitate their survival. After years, even decades, some of these molluscs are able to overcome these barriers and reach for the more exposed and less favourable northern coast. In this case, in almost five years, this species has already colonized the entire Ría de Arousa.

Pending the obtaining of more data and observation of whether native nudibranch species are displaced, the authors do not consider it problematic nowadays.

It cannot be ruled out the possibility that there may be another species of *Dendrodoris* such as *D. temarana* Pruvot-Fol, 1953 among the specimens observed and photographed in Arousa, but not preserved. This would have to be confirmed by molecular analysis.

This would be, therefore, the confirmation that this species is found in Galicia, that its populations are maintained over time, and that it is expanding rapidly throughout the Ría de Arousa.

(Right page) Figure 4. *Dendrodoris limbata*. A-C: specimens from Intertidal Natural Space Umia-O Grove-A Lanzada, Pontevedra; D: specimens from Arousa Island, Pontevedra; E: specimen from the Ribeira marina, Ría de Arousa, A Coruña. Approximate sizes between 5 and 10 cm.

Figura 4. *Dendrodoris limbata*. A-C: ejemplares del Complejo Intermareal Umia-O Grove-A Lanzada, Pontevedra; D: ejemplares de la Illa de Arousa, Pontevedra; E: ejemplar del Puerto deportivo de Ribeira, Ría de Arousa, A Coruña. Tamaños aproximados de entre 5 y 10 cm.

Order SIPHONARIIDA
Superfamily SIPHONARIOIDEA
Family SIPHONARIIDAE

Siphonaria pectinata (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 5)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Carnota, Lariño Beach; 42°46'15.25''N, 9°07'17.50''W; 26 Jan. 1991; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Porto do Son, Castro de Baroña; 42°41'39.17''N, 9°01'48.35''W; 1 Feb. 2004; J.E. Trigo leg. • 5 specimens; A Coruña, Corrubedo, Balieiros Beach; 42°34'47.06''N, 9°04'47.20''W; 6 Jul. 2016; J.E. Trigo leg. • 6 specimens; A Coruña, Corrubedo, Corrubedo Beach; 42°34'37.41''N, 9°03'42.51''W; 31 Mar. 2019; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, O Grove, San Vicente do Mar; Pedras Negras Beach; 42°27'20.14''N, 8°55'18.38''W; 18 May 2010; J.E. Trigo leg. • 26 specimens; Pontevedra, Sanxenxo, A Lapa Beach; 42°26'09.11''N, 8°52'17.21''W; 1 Apr. 2025; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, Aldán, Pintens Beach; 42°17'00.58''N, 8°49'57.72''W; 8 Dec. 1987; J.E. Trigo leg. • 20 specimens Pontevedra, Aldán, Rabáns Beach; 42°17'57.15''N, 8°50'56.80''W; 14 Oct. 2024; J. E. Trigo leg. • 17 specimens; Pontevedra, Aldán, Area Brava Beach; 42°17'27.56''N, 8°50'22.34''W; 14 Oct. 2024; J. E. Trigo leg. • 6 specimens; Pontevedra, Baiona; 42°06'47.02''N, 8°53'12.32''W; 19, Mar. 1980; E. Rolán leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, A Guarda, Area Grande Beach; 41°54'36.65''N, 8°52'36.74''W; 28 Aug. 2009; J.E. Trigo leg.

Shell: Conical, irregular and with a central apex. Somewhat rough outer surface with radiated striations varying in thickness. Very dark brown interior, with a shiny surface and the muscular impression interrupted on the right side. Yellow or whitish central area.

Known distribution: Atlantic, from Angola to the north of the Iberian Peninsula. Also in the western Mediterranean (POPPE & GOTO, 1991; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; TRIGO ET AL., 2018; MUÑOZ ET AL., 2019). There are also some sporadic records of this

species in central Mediterranean areas such as Tunisia (northern shores up to Cap Bon area), Greece (Saronikos Gulf) and Croatia (Split area) where it is recognized as an allochthonous species (CROCETTA, 2016).

Remarks: Species to be sporadically found in the late 60s in intertidal pools located in supratidal areas of the southern coast of Galicia, between A Guarda and Baiona (ROLÁN, 1983). The hypothesis of its appearance in this area at that time was attributed to the fact that since it was a species of planctotrophic devel-

(Right page) Figure 5. *Siphonaria pectinata*. A: intertidal pools with sand and marks left by this species, where no other invertebrates coexist, Caldebarcos, Carnota, A Coruña; B: intertidal pond in Lariño, A Coruña, with the same marks, C-F: intertidal summer pools in Lariño, A Coruña, with high concentrations of this species, which have finally displaced typical native ones; G: intertidal pools in Corrubedo, A Coruña, although the population density drastically lowers over winter, a large number of specimens can be easily noticed onto the sampled rocks; H: A Lapa Beach, Sanxenxo, Pontevedra, small specimens begin to develop very quickly after winter. (Approximate size of shells between 5 and 25 mm).

(Página derecha) Figura 5. *Siphonaria pectinata*. A: charcas intermareales con arena y marcas dejadas por esta especie, donde ningún otro invertebrado marino coexiste con ella, Caldebarcos, Carnota, A Coruña; B: charca intermareal en Lariño, A Coruña, con las mismas huellas; C-F: charcas intermareales en verano, Lariño, A Coruña, con alta concentración de ejemplares de esta especie, que finalmente ha terminado por desplazar a las nativas; G: charcas intermareales en Corrubedo, A Coruña, aunque la densidad de ejemplares cae drásticamente en invierno, se puede observar fácilmente una gran cantidad de individuos en las rocas muestreadas; H: playa de A Lapa, Sanxenxo, Pontevedra, pequeños ejemplares comienzan a desarrollarse rápidamente tras el invierno. (Tamaño aproximado de las conchas entre 5 y 25 mm).

opment, some larvae likely to have arrived from the southern Portuguese coast could settle only in pools where water was heated by the sun and practically no contact with the seawater surrounding them. The usual temperature of the seawater in Galicia kept them relegated to the aforementioned coastal area, exclusively and only in isolated spots. Two decades later, in 1987, some specimens were located in Aldán Cove, in Ría de Pontevedra, and in 1988 in the town of Lariño (OTERO & TRIGO, 1989), at the northern end of Ría de Muros, indicating already the increasing temperatures registered of marine waters.

Currently, this species can be found from A Guarda, at the mouth of Miño River, along the border with Portugal, to Costa da Morte. In some places, the enormous quantities found are worrying, being the density of specimens so

great that no native species were observed in the pools, in which, previously and, above all, the families Patellidae, Trochidae and Littorinidae were common. In the sampling on this species carried out outside Galicia, data have been obtained along the Portuguese and Spanish coasts up to Gibraltar, also on the Canary Islands, specifically on the islands of Lanzarote, La Graciosa, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria and Tenerife. In none of these sampled places have been observed such high densities of *S. pectinata* as in the pools on the coast of Galicia, being this fact very surprising since this immigrant species comes from much warmer areas.

This is, therefore, the furthest northern record in the European Atlantic registered in its natural range for this species.

Class BIVALVIA
Subclass AUTOBRANCHIA
Order MYTILIDA
Family MYTILIDAE

Crenella arenaria Monterosato, 1875 (Fig. 6A, B)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Laxe, Laxe harbour; 43°13'26.91"N, 9°00'08.52"W; 11 Apr. 2008; J.E. Trigo leg. • 2 valves; A Coruña, Caldebarcos, Carnota Beach; 42°50'31.81"N, 9°06'29.89"O; 18 Sep. 2024; J.E. Trigo leg.

Shell: Up to 3 mm; outline obliquely drop-shaped to trapezoid, beak moderately broad; shell smooth, thin, shiny and translucent with prominent umbos and numerous and very fine growth lines. Hinge with 6-7 tiny teeth.

Known distribution: There is very little information available on this species. It is recorded for the Mediterranean (POPPE & GOTO, 1993), the Azores (MARTINS ET AL. 2009), for the Atlantic only in Madeira (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011) and for Portugal, the Azores and the Canary Islands: Fuerteventura (HERNÁNDEZ ET AL. 2011).

Ecology: Although it is not known for certain, probably in small holes in rocks

with fine sediment from a few metres deep onwards.

Remarks: It should be noted that, although it is cited in the Azores, this might be a confusion with the species *Rhomboidella canariensis* (Odhner, 1932) that lives in the Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Archipelagos (DELONGUEVILLE, SCALET & SWINNEN, 2019). The difference between it and *C. arenaria* is that the sculpture of the latter, as indicated above, consists exclusively of very fine growth lines, while the former has radial striations (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011).

This is, therefore, the first record for Galicia and the furthest northern record registered for this species.

Figure 6. A, B: *Crenella arenaria*, specimen from Laxe, A Coruña. (1.55 mm); C, D: *Modiolus adriaticus*, specimen from Sada, A Coruña (67.5 mm); E, F: *Modiolus adriaticus*, specimen from Ría de Vigo, Pontevedra (38.5 mm).

Figura 6. A, B: *Crenella arenaria*, exemplar de Laxe, A Coruña (1,55 mm); C, D: *Modiolus adriaticus*, exemplar de Sada, A Coruña (67,5 mm); E, F: *Modiolus adriaticus*, exemplar de la Ría de Vigo, Pontevedra (38,5 mm).

Family MODIOLIDAE

Modiolus adriaticus Lamarck, 1819 (Fig. 6C-F)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ferrol, Narón. 43°29'54.02"N, 8°10'19.76"W; 9 Feb. 2022; J.E. Trigo and J. García leg. • 27 specimens; A Coruña, Sada, Sada Beach; 43°21'00.33"N, 8°15'02.88"W; Feb. 2019; A. Trincado leg. • 38 specimens; same data as for preceding; Mar. 2019; A.

Trincado leg. • 52 specimens; same data as for preceding; Apr. 2019; A. Trincado leg. • 14 specimens; same data as for preceding; Jan. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 23 specimens; same data as for preceding; Feb. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 37 specimens; same data as for preceding; Feb. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 45 specimens; same data as for preceding; Mar. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 5 specimens; same data as for preceding; Apr. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 42 specimens; same data as for preceding; Jan. 2021; A. Trincado leg. • 13 specimens; same data as for preceding; Feb. 2020; A. Trincado leg. • 16 specimens; same data as for preceding; Jan. 2022; A. Trincado leg. • 5 specimens; same data as for preceding; Apr. 2023; A. Trincado leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Porto do Son, Castro de Baroña; 42°41'39.17"N, 9°01'48.35"W; 14 Jul. 1987; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Corrubedo, Balieiros Beach; 42°34'47.06"N, 9°04'47.20"W; 14 Jul. 2002. J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Rianxo, Rianxo harbour; 42°38'57.14"N, 8°49'23.23"W; 16 Sept. 2025; Juan Carlos González leg.

Shell: Elongate oval, equivalve and equilateral, with subterminal apex. Margin smooth. Hinge not crenulated. Colouring highly variable, from red to bright yellow, even with greyish shades throughout and sometimes with some dark lines running from the umbo to the posterior edge of the valve. Periostracum thin, very adherent and smooth.

Known distribution: Mediterranean and Black Sea. Atlantic from Norway to Gibraltar. Also on the Azores (TEBBLE, 1966; HIDALGO, 1917; POPPE & GOTO, 1993; MACEDO *ET AL.*, 1999; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018).

Ecology: In Galicia, in the Rías Baixas, it is relatively common to find small red or reddish specimens that are usually found buried in sand at different depths and with a maximum length of 3 cm. In the Ártabro Gulf (Rías Altas), however, it has been found that specimens are usually larger than 6 cm in length, reaching a maximum of seven, a great difference in size for what is supposed to be the same species. The colouring of these specimens is always greyish, with some being almost black and always attached to the area closest to the rhizome of the marine phanerogams of the genus *Zostera*, whereas the red and smallest specimens are always found buried in sand.

Although species of the order Mytilida, with four different families in Europe, are well known, it is still surprising that a new species has recently been described (OCKELMANN & CEDHAGEN, 2019) in the waters of the Kattegat and Skagerrak straits between Denmark, Sweden and Norway, named *Modiolus cimbricus* Ockelmann & Cedhagen, 2019.

Remarks: Live specimens were collected in the area of Sada (A Coruña) and DNA tests were carried out. The results obtained showed a 98.77% similarity with the existing data in the BOLD platform for *M. adriaticus*, which falls within the co-specific range.

A subspecies is known from the southern part of the United Kingdom, *M. adriaticus ovalis* G.B. Sowerby II, 1859, which has a darker periostracum that can be almost black. It is said to be larger, reaching 5 cm or more (TEBBLE, 1966), and slightly more oval and globose than the usual form of the species (POPPE & GOTO, 1993). All this is consistent with the specimens found in the Sada area, but its validity as a subspecies is not recognised. Until new data are obtained for this subspecies, it will be considered as a mere morphotype of *M. adriaticus*.

Order ARCIDA
Superfamily ARCOIDEA
Family GLYCYMERIDIDAE

Glycymeris bimaculata (Poli, 1795) (Fig. 7A-C)

Material examined: Galicia • 7 valves; A Coruña, Mugarbos, A Bestarruza beach. 43°27'40.90"N, 8°15'44.79"W; 18 Jun. 2025; J.E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ribeira, Rúa Island. 42°32'52.62"N, 8°56'24.17"W; 22 Jul. 2017; J. Pérez leg.

Figure 7. A-C: *Glycymeris bimaculata*, Rúa Island, Ría de Arousa, A Coruña, external, internal and front views (length 79 mm); D-F: *Glycymeris glycymeris*, Malpica, A Coruña, external, internal and front views (length 76 mm).

Figura 7. A-C: *Glycymeris bimaculata*, Isla de Rúa, Ría de Arousa, A Coruña, vistas externa, interna y frontal (longitud 76 mm); D-F: *Glycymeris glycymeris*, Malpica, A Coruña, vistas externa, interna y frontal (longitud 76 mm).

Shell: very large, heavy and thick, not as globose as *Glycymeris pilosa* (Linnaeus, 1767). Outline almost circular. Beaks and

umbones raising a little above the ligamental area. Very slightly opisthogyrate, nearly orthogyrate. Many narrow and dis-

tinct radiating ribs are separated by very fine grooves. Concentric little ribs are obsolete and often repressed, resulting in an undulating sculpture of irregular lines.

Known distribution: In the Atlantic, from southern Portugal and northwest Morocco to the Canary Islands and also in the Mediterranean (HIDALGO, 1917; NORDSIECK, 1969; PARENZAN, 1970-76; SALAS, 1996; MACEDO ET AL., 1999; POPPE & GOTO, 1993; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; NOLF & SWINNEN, 2013).

In our area, a specimen measuring 90 mm in diameter was found alive in the Ría de Arousa, specifically on the Isla de Rúa (Pontevedra), at a depth of 20 metres in sandy bottom, thus confirming the presence of this species in Galicia.

Remarks: A large number of specimens of the genus *Glycymeris* have been collected in the last two decades all over Galicia and even Asturias. It is a very common genus in this area and unlike other bivalve species, which prefer the Rías Baixas, or even smaller upper estuaries, because they offer large sandy and muddy areas with important natural protection, this genus can be found throughout Galicia with great ease. Is an appreciated culinary species that commonly found for sale in the fish markets among other species of bivalves. The great variability in the pattern of the specimens that can be found in Galicia is a factor that has led to confusion and the species cited in Galicia until now were *Glycymeris glycymeris* (Linnaeus, 1767) (HIDALGO, 1917; ROLÁN, 1983; TRIGO ET AL., 2018) and *G. pilosa*, the latter only

cited by Hidalgo (1917) in Vigo. Specimens with a more extended periostracum on the valves are common in our study area, as well as others with very strongly marked brownish internal colourations. In the Ría de Arousa, about ten of them, which morphologically presented all the characteristics of the latter species, were determined by DNA analysis to correspond to *G. glycymeris*, it is not so clear that the latter can be present in Galicia. Until more extensive studies are carried out, it is therefore not possible to affirm that this is a species that can be found in our area.

Continuing with the verifications, the microsculpture of the shell of the specimen obtained in Rúa Island was observed under magnification, and it could be seen that there were clear differences with *G. glycymeris*. The pattern and colouring with very clearly marked and visible growth lines and with a white or yellowish-white spot in the umbo area are morphological characters that differentiate clearly *G. glycymeris* from *G. bimaculata*.

In recent sampling carried out in the ría of Ferrol, up to seven *G. bimaculata* valves have been found washed up on A Bestarruza beach, suggesting that this may be a well-established species in Galician waters, but one that had not been taken into account until now due to its close resemblance to *G. glycymeris*.

No references have been found in the bibliography consulted, so this is the first record for Galicia, and it is also the northernmost limit known for this species.

Order CARDITIDA
Family CARDITIDAE

Cardita calyculata (Linnaeus, 1758) (Fig. 8A-C)

Material examined: Galicia • 3 specimens; A Coruña, Covas, Santa Comba Beach; 43°33'21.26''N, 8°17'25.67''W; 23 Apr. 2024; A. Trincado leg.

Shell: Equivalve, inequilateral, trapezoidal in shape and with subterminal apices. Sculpture formed by numerous and very thick radial ribs occasionally bearing small scales. Crenulated margin.

Whitish or yellowish in colour, sometimes with brownish spots.

Known distribution: From Galicia to Senegal in the Atlantic, and on the Azores, Madeira and the Canary

Figure 8. A-C: *Cardita calyculata*, specimens from Santa Comba beach, Ferrol, A Coruña (2.7, 2.5 and 2.6 mm); D-F: *Vasconiella jeffreysiana*, right valves (D, E) from Arteixo beach, A Coruña (length 2.5 mm) and left valve (F) from América beach, Pontevedra (length 3.3 mm).

Figura 8. A-C: *Cardita calyculata*, exemplar de la playa de Santa Comba, Ferrol, A Coruña (2.7, 2.5 y 2.6 mm); D-F: *Vasconiella jeffreysiana*, valvas derechas (D, E) de la playa de Arteixo, A Coruña (longitud 2,5 mm) y valva izquierda (F) de playa América, Pontevedra (longitud 3,3 mm).

Islands. Also in the Mediterranean (HIDALGO, 1917; POPPE & GOTO, 1993; MACEDO *ET AL.*, 1999; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018).

Ecology: Always under rocks and stones or in small patches of sand covering some very exposed rock crevices. Sometimes among colonies of *Mytilus* and among algae of the genera *Corallina* and *Cystoseira*, from low tide level up to 20 meters deep.

Remarks: Until now, this species could be found in Galicia in some isolated points on the north coast of the Ría de Muros. Also on the south coast, from Castro de Baroña in Porto do Son to the lighthouse in Corrubedo, both in A Coruña. In the Ría de Arousa in very isolated points near Santa Uxía de Ribeira, A Coruña (TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018) and also in the Ría de Vigo, Pontevedra, but only on Toralla Island (ROLÁN,

OTERO & ROLÁN, 1998). All these sites are located in the Rías Baixas area.

Three juveniles of this species have been found for the first time in an area outside the Rías Baixas. Over the years, sampling carried out in nearby areas (OTERO & TRIGO, 1986; URGORRI, TRONCOSO & DOBARRO, 1992; OLABARRÍA, TRONCOSO & URGORRI, 1995; 1997; OLABARRÍA, URGORRI & TRONCOSO, 1997; TRONCOSO, MOREIRA & URGORRI, 2005; VARELA, MOREIRA & URGORRI, 2009) do not cite this species, so we can affirm that this is a new current colonisation. The possibility that it is a colonisation coming from Cantabrian waters does not seem possible. The only known record of this species is a single valve found in Villaviciosa, Asturias (ALONSO & RAVEN, 2020).

In the entire intermediate area between the Rías Baixas and the Ártabra coast, the presence of this species has not been detected. We cannot explain such a wide geographical jump, although the development of its juvenile stages goes through a trochophore phase, continued by a veliger, which gives it a wider colonisation faculty than other species of direct development. The subtle warming of the marine waters around Galicia may be allowing this species, and others discussed in this work, to reach areas where it was not possible before, as the larvae could not survive the conditions found further north.

The distribution of this species in Galicia is extended from the Rías Baixas to the Ártabra coast.

Vasconiella jeffreysiana (P. Fischer, 1873) (Fig. 8D-F)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 right valve; A Coruña, Covas, Santa Comba Beach; 43°33'21.26''N, 8°17'25.67''W; M. Suárez leg. • 3 right valves; A Coruña, Arteixo, Sabón Beach; 43°19'42.87''N, 8°30'27.11''W; A. Trincado leg. • 2 left valves; Pontevedra, Nigrán, América Beach; 42°06'47.98''N, 8°49'44.88''W; 23 May 2018; Juan E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg.

Shell: Circular in shape. Shell with very unequal valves. The left one rounded and the right one slightly smaller and convex with a deep indentation on the ventral side. The left shell is roughly circular and almost flat, with multiple concentric growth lines very clearly visible. Size up to 5 mm.

Known distribution: The species is distributed in the eastern Atlantic, from the Bay of Biscay as far north as Morocco and the westernmost and easternmost Mediterranean (POPPE & GOTO, 1993; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; MUÑOZ ET AL., 2019).

Remarks: Unmistakable species. The three shells collected on Sabón beach,

adjacent to the outer harbour of A Coruña, were taken in three different samplings. One of the dykes in the port prevents the natural circulation of the predominant sea currents in the area, which causes a progressive accumulation of sand against it. The sand, which may come from a certain depth, accumulates and it is common for large quantities of molluscs of different species and, above all, micro-molluscs, to appear there. The valves found on América Beach, however, were among the substrate obtained in a series of samplings carried out on the same day.

This is the first record for Galicia.

Order CARDIIDA

Acanthocardia spinosa ([Lightfoot], 1786) (Fig. 9)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, O Grove; 42°29'13.89''N, 8°53'21.96''W; 24 Apr. 2024; C. Mariño leg.

Figure 9. *Acanthocardia spinosa*. A-G: specimen from O Grove, Pontevedra, taken alive.
Figura 9. *Acanthocardia spinosa*. A-G: *ejemplar de O Grove, Pontevedra, hallado vivo.*

Shell: Large, robust, equilateral and inequilateral. Thirty-two to thirty-seven fine ribs with a large number of small, cone-shaped tubercles.

Known distribution: Mediterranean (POPPE & GOTO, 1993; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011) and near Atlantic north to Sesimbra, Portugal (MACEDO *ET AL.*,

1999; GRALHO, 2011), and south to Madeira (SEGERS, SWINNEN & ABREU, 2009). Hidalgo (1917) cites it in Sagres, Portugal. We know of no other records further north than Sesimbra.

Ecology: It lives in muddy, sandy or mixed bottoms in the infralitoral and circalitoral levels up to 120 metres deep.

Remarks: The specimen found in O Grove is a large albino specimen, estimated to be between 5 and 10 years old, so it is likely that there is a stable population of this species in the area. The resemblance to other *Acanthocardia*, which are very abundant in the Arousa estuary, could be the reason

for which that this species goes completely unnoticed. In fact, this specimen was initially identified in the fish auction as *Acanthocardia echinata* Linnaeus, 1758.

This is a new record for Galicia and its most northerly distribution limit observed for this species.

Family SEMELIDAE

Ervilia castanea (Montagu, 1803) (Fig. 10)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Ribeira, Couso Beach; 42°31'11.10"N, 9°02'20.54"W; 22 May 2007; J. E. Trigo leg. • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, O Grove, a Toxa Island; 42°29'13.62"N, 8°51'19.09"W; 10 Jul. 2024; J. Fernández leg. • 2 valves; Pontevedra, Vigo, Cíes Islands, San Martiño Island; 42°11'50.97"N, 8°53'35.58"W; 22 Oct. 2019; J. E. Trigo, L. Rodríguez and F. Febrero leg.

Shell: Up to 15 mm in length. Equivalve and inequilateral. Umbo displaced towards the anterior half, opisthogyric. Sculpture of fine growth striae. Colouring brown or sometimes whitish.

Known distribution: from the south of the British Isles to the central Mediterranean (MUÑOZ ET AL. 2019) and Black Sea (MACEDO ET AL., 1999). Also in the Azores and Madeira and the Canary Islands (TEBBLE, 1966; POPPE & GOTO, 1993), up to Senegal (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; COSEL & GOFAS, 2019), although it is not very clear whether these are fossils (RODRÍGUEZ BABÍO & BONNIN, 1987). This species has been recorded in Galicia in the Vigo and Arousa Rías (HIDALGO, 1917; CADÉE, 1969; MOREIRA & TRONCOSO, 2007).

Ecology: A live specimen in the Cova cove, Muros, A Coruña, was dredged in the 80s at a depth of about 10 metres on the maërl bottom, but the data and the specimen have been lost. The specimen found in Couso was found completely with both valves, but without soft parts, washed ashore of the beach. The valves found in Cíes were dredged at a depth of 8 metres on a gravel and sandy bottom. Another whole specimen taken alive was collected in O Grove in sand bottom, at two meters depth.

Remarks: Cited in the Ría de Vigo as *Iphigenia* sp. (ROLÁN ET AL., 1989) on the

basis of loose valves obtained near the Cíes Islands, all of which were whitish in colour. It was then thought that they belonged to an unidentified species due to the morphological similarities with African species of the same genus. The only thing that did not fit was the size, as the latter are much larger than the specimens found in Galicia. The possibility that it could be the species *E. castanea* simply because of its colour was not taken into account, as the specimens that can be found in relatively nearby areas such as Portugal or the United Kingdom are all dark brown in colour. Moreover, this species can be found in large numbers, whereas this is not the case in Galicia. This whitish colour may have led to its identification elsewhere in Europe as *Ervilia nitens* (Montagu, 1808), an American species first described in Dunbar, Scotland. Subsequently, after this species was not found again in European waters, it was concluded that it had arrived in that Scottish port in ballast sand from the Caribbean (FORBES & HANLEY, 1853). Other authors who doubted that it ever actually existed in British or European waters supported the hypothesis of Forbes and Hanley (ROOIJ-SCHUILING, 1973; DAVIS, 1973; MORTON & SCOTT, 1990). Even so, there are records of this species in Portugal (ALVES ET AL., 2003),

Figure 10. A, B: *Ervilia castanea*, Couso, Ribeira, A Coruña (length 6 mm); C: specimen from O Grove taken alive (length 8 mm); D, E: valve from Cíes Islands.

Figura 10. A, B: Ervilia castanea, Couso, Ribeira, A Coruña (longitud 6mm); C: ejemplar de O Grove encontrado vivo (longitud 8 mm); D, E: valva de las Islas Cíes.

and it is possible that they are, in fact, white specimens like those found in Galicia.

Its presence is confirmed in Vigo and Arousa Rías, and its distribution is

extended to the Ría de Muros, with a live dredged specimen, that is, to practically the whole of Rías Baixas.

Its presence in Galicia is certified and its correct determination is clarified.

Order VENERIDA
Family MACTRIDAE

Eastonia rugosa (Helbling, 1779) (Fig. 11)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; A Coruña, Miño, Alameda Beach; 43°20'22.58''N, 8°12'16.18''W; 8 Jan. 2014; M. Suárez leg. • 8 specimens; A Coruña, Bergondo, O Regueiro Beach; 43°19'59.30''N, 8°13'14.16''W; 4 Feb. 2019; A. Trincado leg. • 34 specimens; Same data as for preceding; 20 Feb. 2019; A. Trincado leg. • 7 specimens; same data as for preceding; 31 Aug. 2019; A. Trincado leg.

Shell: Equivalve, inequilateral, solid, but sometimes not very thick. Oval profile with somewhat truncated rear edge. Hinge with a solid, well developed cardinal plate. Coarse sculpture with numerous radial ribs intersecting with somewhat distinct growth lines. Crenulated margin. Periostracum very thin. Whitish or brownish colour.

Animal: Whitish, with a long siphon, covered with tiny tubercles, narrow and very dark brown.

Known distribution: In the Atlantic, from Galicia to Equatorial Guinea, including the Canary Islands and Cape Verde. In the Mediterranean, on the coasts of Tunisia, Algeria and the Iberian Peninsula, as far as Italy and also found in the Balearic Islands (POPPE & GOTO, 1993; MACEDO *ET AL.*, 1999; ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI, 2004; LÓPEZ, QUIÑONERO & TARRUELLA, 2010; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018).

Records of this species in Galicia are scarce. Hidalgo (1917) mention it in Bayona, Betanzos, Carril, Coruña and Vigo. He refers to the fact that Mac Andrew was not able to find more than loose valves, and points out that it undoubtedly inhabits the coast of Algiers. In more recent works there is also no evidence that living specimens have been found (ROLÁN MOSQUERA, OTERO SCHMITT & ROLÁN ÁLVAREZ, 1989; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018).

Ecology: In this case, in the sampling carried out in the Ría de Betanzos it was

possible to collect a total of 36 specimens of *E. rugosa* with both valves on, of which, 14 of them were alive or with remains of the soft parts. They were found in different samplings separated in time and in two different points of the estuary.

The first three live specimens of this species were found in a very specific area: the Ría de Betanzos. The first discovery was made in January 2014, after a deep storm that affected the coast of Galicia. One of the authors, found it washed ashore and alive on the Alameda beach, Miño, A Coruña. The specimen, once the soft parts had been removed, was deposited in the museum 'Mares de Cedeira' in the town of Cedeira, A Coruña.

In February 2019, another author, carrying out a sampling on the O Regueiro beach, in Gandarío, where it is possible to find numerous loose valves of this species, specifically in an area of thick conchiferous detritus surrounded by rocks and an area of just over 1 m², found a total of 34 specimens with both valves on, one of them with remains of the animal where the very dark brown siphons can be seen and was preserved in alcohol. The discovery was made after a heavy storm, so all the specimens were partially unearthed.

The third of the findings is a small specimen that was found alive on the same O Regueiro beach in August 2019, buried at a depth of 10-15 cm in an area of very compacted gravel.

(Right page) Figure 11. A-L: *Eastonia rugosa*, specimens collected on O Regueiro beach, Sada, A Coruña; M: one of the specimens found alive; N: empty shells found in their natural habitat, O Regueiro beach.

Figura 11. A-L: *Eastonia rugosa*, ejemplares recogidos en la playa O Regueiro, Sada, A Coruña; M: uno de los ejemplares hallados vivos; N: conchas vacías halladas en su hábitat natural, playa de O Regueiro.

Since 2019, more and more specimens have been gradually found between Gandarío and Sada on very compacted gravel bottoms that are exposed between tides.

Remarks: Although *E. rugosa* is not a common species in Galicia, it is possible to find occasional loose valves, usually found washed ashore on beaches. Specimens have also been found with both valves, but without the remains of soft parts, so it was assumed that the presence of this species in Galicia was through subfossil specimens buried in the substratum, as no live specimens had been documented to date.

The hypotheses considered so far regarding the existence of living or non-living specimens in Galicia conclude that, being an essentially thermophilic species, its range of distribution would vary with respect to the global climate. Thus, there may have been times when its distribution range reached the coasts of Galicia and possibly even other more northerly latitudes, but until recently the average water temperatures kept it further south. It is currently in a phase of expansion after having survived in

small groups and in very specific points thanks to the warming of the waters, which has allowed a new colonisation (LA VALLE *ET AL.*, 2007).

Local fishermen indicate that they have been familiar with this species for decades and have even consumed it, although it is true that they do not refer to it in large quantities. They always give references to a few isolated specimens found. We do not know whether these indications are reliable as it is common for the public to confuse different species, but some of them described the dark-coloured siphon as a clear identification sign in the specimens collected, which coincides with the actual colour of the siphons of *E. rugosa*.

This species has not been found alive before as it is restricted to a very small geographical area, living buried in the substratum between 15 and 20 cm in areas of conchiferous detritus or mud from the low intertidal zone to the infralitoral zone.

This is the first record of stable living populations in Galicia and its northernmost distribution observed for this species.

Mactra glauca Born, 1778 (Fig. 12)

Material examined: Galicia • 1 specimen; Pontevedra, O Grove, Mexilloeira Beach; 42°28'44.51''N, 8°54'27.80''W; 22 Oct. 2024; C. Mariño leg.

Shell: Wide, triangular, slender and shiny. Up to 120 mm long. Creamy white shell with darker coloured lines from the umbo towards the ventral area. Periostracum brown and interior light brown to white.

Known distribution: From southern England to Morocco (TEBBLE, 1966). Cantabric Sea (HIDALGO, 1917). Also in the Mediterranean (POPPE & GOTO, 1993; MUÑOZ *ET AL.*, 2019) and the Canary Islands (GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011).

Ecology: Known to inhabit sandy bottoms to a depth of 50 metres.

Remarks: Until now, the existing records of this species have referred to loose valves found in different parts of the coast of Galicia, such as the Ártabro

Gulf and Carnota (TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2010; TRIGO *ET AL.*, 2018).

There have also been references on the internet, specifically in the Cíes Islands, located at the entrance of the Ría de Vigo (ASTURNATURA, 2015) and on loose valves.

The large size of the valves makes this species practically unmistakable once they have been collected from beaches. When thrown away, they can go unnoticed, as their appearance is very similar to the valves of *Callista chione* (Linnaeus, 1758) and other large bivalve species.

After suspicions that there could be colonies or live specimens scattered around different points of the Galician

Figure 12. *Mactra glauca*, specimen from Mexiloeira beach, O Grove, Pontevedra. A, B: external and internal view; C, D: detail of the hinge; E: living animal with extended siphons.

Figura 12. *Mactra glauca*, exemplar de playa Mexiloeira, O Grove, Pontevedra. A, B: vista externa e interna; C, D: detalle de la charnela; E: animal vivo con los sifones extendidos.

coast, we did not go beyond this point since to date it had not been possible to find any. Unlike other species that have appeared in that same area, but that had never been found in Galicia before, not even loose valves, nor any other trace, with the discovery of the live specimen referred to in this work, it is possible to ensure its presence in our waters. The adult specimen, 94 mm long, suggests

that there may be others in that area, or even a colony, but the geography of the Galician coast and the difficulty of access to certain areas does not make it easy to find them.

The specimen was found in an area near Mexilloeira Beach, 8 m deep on a sandy bottom.

This is the first record of this living species in Galicia.

Doubtful and foreign species (Fig. 13)

In addition to the species mentioned above, other species have been found that, for now, will be considered for informational purposes only, since only a single specimen of each of them has appeared. As long as no more specimens appear, either alive or with soft parts, they will not be taken into account as new records for Galicia. Data on the location of collection and some notes taken are provided if considered interesting.

Others that have been found in different places in Galicia are clearly foreign species and do not form part of the fauna of our coasts, as they are probably specimens from ornaments, necklaces or other decorative objects, or used in certain divinatory arts and purchased in souvenir shops.

The species are as follows:

Ebenomitra ebenus (Lamarck, 1811). One specimen found at Sabón Beach. AT. It is possible that isolated specimens could develop in our area, although

only in very favourable conditions due to a network of factors such as temperature, atmospheric conditions, adequate food and others that are necessarily critical for their development.

Notocochlis gualterianus (Récluz, 1844). One single specimen in perfect condition found in Sabón Beach, A Coruña. AT. It is possible that a species such as this could form stable colonies in our area, as it is the case of *Naticarius stercusmuscarum* (Gmelin, 1791), native to the Mediterranean that has been established in the Ría de Arousa (Horro & Rolán, 2011). However, until more specimens are found, or perhaps even a living one, we do not consider this record to be valid.

Naticarius hebraeus (Marty, 1786). One specimen provided by a citizen from the town of Baiona, Pontevedra in 2019. According to her, she found it on the beach, washed ashore. As long as no more specimens are found, we do not

(Right page) Figure 13. Doubtful and foreign species. A: *Ebenomitra ebenus*, specimen found on Sabón beach, A Coruña; B: *Notocochlis gualterianus*, specimen found on Sabón beach, A Coruña; C: *Naticarius hebraeus*, found in Concheiras beach, Baiona, Pontevedra; D: *Nassarius globosus* found in Langosteira beach, Fisterra, A Coruña; E: *Rissoa auriscalpium*, specimen found on Ponzos beach, A Coruña; F: *Gafrarium pectinatum* found in Areoso Island, Ría de Arousa, Pontevedra; G: *Rocellaria dubia*, broken valve from Cíes Islands.

(Página derecha) Figura 13. Especies dudosas y foráneas. A: *Ebenomitra ebenus*, ejemplar encontrado en la playa de Sabón, A Coruña; B: *Notocochlis gualterianus*, ejemplar encontrado en la playa de Sabón, A Coruña; C: *Naticarius hebraeus* encontrado en la playa de As Concheiras, Baiona, Pontevedra; D: *Nassarius globosus* encontrado en la playa de Langosteira, Fisterra, A Coruña; E: *Rissoa auriscalpium*, ejemplar encontrado en la playa de Ponzos, A Coruña; F: *Gafrarium pectinatum* encontrado en el islote Areoso, Ría de Arousa, Pontevedra; G: *Rocellaria dubia*, valva rota de las Islas Cíes.

consider the finding as anything more than anecdotal, although another species of this genus from the Mediterranean, *Naticarius stercusmuscarum* (Gmelin, 1791) is naturalised in the waters of the Ría de Arousa.

Rissoa auriscalpium (Linnaeus, 1758). One single specimen in perfect condition found in Miño, A Coruña, Alameda Beach. AT.

The specimen was mixed with species of native micromolluscs thrown at the tide line. It is possible that, under very favourable natural conditions, isolated specimens of this species could survive and develop in Galician waters, as the previous species.

Although it is a species strictly associated with *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) Delile, 1813, a marine phanerogam endemic to the Mediterranean, it is possible that exceptional specimens capable of surviving in the Atlantic area may feed on other species of phanerogams native to Galician waters, such as *Zostera marina* Linnaeus, 1753 or *Zostera noltii* Hornemann, 1832.

Nassarius globosus (Quoy & Gaimard, 1833) one specimen of in perfect condition was found on Langosteira Beach, Fisterra. As it is a species with an exclusive distribution in the Indo-Pacific, its appearance in Galicia cannot be considered natural. It is not the first time that certain very common exotic specimens appear in tourist souvenir shops coming mostly from Philippines, especially in the last two decades. This fact has a very direct relationship with *Santería*, which has a wide following in our community due to the large number of migrants who have arrived from countries such as Brazil, Cuba, México or Venezuela where it is very widespread and in which marine gastropods are used for certain divination rites.

DISCUSSION

In this work a total of 14 species are studied, 5 gastropods and 9 bivalves.

Barbatia barbata (Linnaeus, 1758). Southern Cíes Island. One valve. Whole specimens with both valves were seen more than 2 decades ago in the collection of an amateur collector from Ribeira, A Coruña, with no annotated data of any kind, although he claimed that they were from the outermost part of the Ría de Arousa. It was not taken into consideration at that time, but now that this valve has been found, it is possible that it could be a species that inhabits the waters of the outer areas of the Rías Baixas, which means minimum depths of between 50 and 100 metres.

This valve was broken during handling for photography.

Gafrarium pectinatum (Linnaeus, 1758). Three valves. Areoso Island. Ría de Arousa. 18 July 2024. As in the previous case of *N. globosus*, its presence in Galicia is not natural and it is possible that it has been used in *Santerian*-related activities.

Rocellaria dubia (Pennant, 1777). South Island, Cíes Islands. One broken valve. The shell found is not whole, but it is perfectly identifiable. As it is a species that has been recorded as far away as the Indian Ocean, specifically in Mozambique and as far north as the British Isles, we are within its natural range. We suppose that, like other species of boring bivalves, it is only capable of colonising spaces where the substrate allows it to do so. In Galicia, where most of the substrate is granitic, it is not as suitable place for this species. Although it is very likely that it could inhabit Galician waters, and has been previously cited (HIDALGO, 1917) without specifying in which place or places, no one else has found this species in any known sampling. Doubts remain until more material will be obtained to ensure its presence in Galician waters.

As far as gastropods are concerned, *Philine angulata*, *Philine intricata* and

Jorunna onubensis and are the first records for Galicia.

Siphonaria pectinata has in Galicia the northernmost known natural distribution limit for this species. For *Dendrodoris limbata*, new data are provided, which are considered interesting.

Regarding the bivalves, *Crenella arenaria*, *Glycymeris bimaculata* and *Acanthocardia spinosa* are the first records for Galicia and the northernmost natural distribution limit in Europe. *Vasconiella jeffreysiana* is the first record for Galicia. *Mactra glauca*, *Eastonia rugosa* and *Acanthocardia spinosa* are the first live specimens to be found in Galicia and *Cardita calyculata*, as a biological indicator of rising sea temperatures, appears much further north than previously possible. For the remaining two species, new data are provided, which are considered interesting.

With the finding of these species, it has been confirmed that the subtle warming of the waters is evident. Gradually, more and more species are arriving that have not been able to do so until now. Others that were already there were kept in certain areas where they developed normally, but were never found, not even traces, shells or empty valves of them, outside those areas.

A minimal increase in temperature can lead to the northward advance of species that previously encountered a physical barrier that was impossible to cross.

The danger posed by this warming, moreover, is the fact that potentially harmful species could reach our coasts. The Galician bivalve aquaculture industry for human consumption is a world leader and is not prepared to face the appearance of species that could pose a serious threat. Monoculture of species such as *Mytilus galloprovincialis* is a strategic error. Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture in Galicia could be the solution to avoid possible future problems, but the family structure of the companies that prevail in this sector closes the doors to any kind of dialogue. All that remains is to hope that no possible

pathogen, parasite, exotic life form or physical-chemical conditions that could affect mussel farming ever appear. As in the case of alien and invasive species, public administrations should intervene and implement preventive measures for possible future cases of such unforeseen incidences.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank, first and very especially, to Emilio Rolán Mosquera for all his help, support and suggestions in the identification of species found and in the preparation of the works published in the last 45 years.

To Carlos Mariño Balsa, technical assistance from the Cambados Fishermen's Union by some of the specimens obtained which were object of study in this work.

Serge Gofas from the University of Málaga and to Joaquin López Soriano, from the Autonomous University of Barcelona for their suggestions on some aspects of the writing of this paper.

To Guillermo Díaz Agradas and Marcos Pérez Señarís, from the A Graña Marine Biology Station of the University of Santiago de Compostela in Ferrol, for providing us with some of the photos of the species that have been discussed here.

To Omar Sánchez, from the University of Oviedo, Asturias, for kindly providing us with bibliography and data on some of the species.

To Juan Carlos González from Galician Coast Guard Service.

To Chris C. Miserendino and Dimitri Sotiriou from California (USA) for his help with certain questions related to the translation of technical words of this work.

FUNDING

The work was conducted at the authors' own expense. No external funding was used.

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